

Role of Vidarikandadi Kala Basti in a Patient with Vitamin B12 Deficiency: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Modern dietary patterns have led to a global rise in nutritional deficiencies. Vitamin B12 deficiency, common among vegetarians and those with malabsorption issues, presents with symptoms like paraesthesia, fatigue, and macrocytic anaemia. If left untreated, vitamin B12 deficiency can lead to anemia, as well as nerve and brain damage, which may eventually become irreversible. *Pandu Vyadhi* described in *Ayurvedic* classical texts can be compared to Anemia

Aim: To illustrate the role of *Panchakarma* in managing Vitamin B12 deficiency.

Materials and Methods: A 22-year-old male presented with tingling sensations, fatigue, hair loss, and calf pain for five months. His initial Vitamin B12 level was 12 pg/mL. After injectable supplementation, levels rose to 1233 pg/mL but dropped to 143 pg/mL after discontinuation. *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti*, a classical *Panchakarma* procedure, was given in two sittings.

Results: An increase in Vitamin B12 levels to 266 pg/mL was observed following Basti therapy.

Conclusion: In this patient, *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti* was associated with improvement in clinical symptoms and a modest increase in serum Vitamin B12 levels during follow-up. As a single case report, causality cannot be established, and larger controlled studies are required to evaluate its potential role in the supportive management of Vitamin B12 deficiency.

KEYWORDS: Vitamin B12 deficiency, *Pandu*, *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti*, *Panchakarma*

INTRODUCTION

Pathology of *Pandu* begins, with the dysfunction of *Agni*, formation of *Aam* and in this case disturbance of *Pitta Dosha* that is circulated in the body by aggravated *Vata*. *Pandu Vyadhi* is one of the major disorders which affect the mankind on a large scale. Majority of sufferers happen to be middle aged, females, having *Vatapitta Pradhan Prakruti & Krura Koshtha*.

Types of *Pandu Vyadhi*¹

- 1) *Vataja Pandu*
- 2) *Pittaja Pandu*
- 3) *Kaphaja Pandu*
- 4) *Tridoshaja Pandu*
- 5) *Mrudbhakshanjanya Pandu*

Anemia is the most common disorder of the blood. There are several kinds of anemia produced by a number of underlying cause—

- Due to deficiency of nutrients
- Due to impaired red cell production Iron deficiency anemia
- Due to excessive red cell destruction
- Due to excess blood loss.

Megaloblastic anemia is due to deficiency of folate or Vitamin B12.

Vitamin B12, or cobalamin, is a crucial water-soluble vitamin necessary for DNA synthesis, proper neurological function, and red blood cell formation. Its deficiency is a growing concern globally, affecting an estimated 5-20% of the population, particularly in developing countries and among individuals with dietary restrictions. It is researched that 47% North Indian population is Vitamin B12 deficient.² Vitamin B12 deficiency can lead to haematologic and neurological symptoms. Generally excessive Vitamin B12 is stored in the liver, decreasing the chances of deficiency. However, in cases where Vitamin B12 cannot be absorbed like dietary insufficiency, malabsorption, depleted hepatic stores and thus leads to its deficiency.^{3,4,5}

Etiological Factors in Vitamin B12 Deficiency

1. **Dietary Insufficiency:** The primary source of Vitamin B12 is animal-based foods like meat, eggs and dairy products. Hence, vegetarians and vegans are particularly vulnerable to deficiency.
2. **Malabsorption Syndromes:** Conditions such as pernicious anemia, atrophic gastritis, celiac disease, Crohn's disease, or post-gastrointestinal surgeries impair Vitamin B12 absorption by reducing intrinsic factor production or disrupting intestinal function.
3. **Chronic Medication Use:** Prolonged usage of antacids, proton pump inhibitors, and metformin can interfere with Vitamin B12 absorption.

Clinical Manifestations: Vitamin B12 deficiency presents with a spectrum of symptoms that affect the neurological, hematological, and systemic systems:

Neurological Symptoms: Tingling or numbness (paraesthesia), cognitive impairment etc. Severe deficiency can lead to irreversible damage to the nervous system.⁶

Haematological Signs: Macrocytic anaemia, fatigue, dizziness, and pallor.

Systemic Effects: Hair loss, generalized muscle pain and weakness.

Conventional Treatment Challenges

The conventional approach typically involves oral, nasal spray or injectable Vitamin B12 supplementation. While these methods address immediate deficiencies, they often fail to prevent recurrence post-treatment. This indicates a need for integrative management approaches targeting both absorption and sustainable nutrient levels.

Case Presentation:

Patient Details:

- Age/Gender: 22 years, Male
- Location: Dehradun, India

Presenting Complaints (since 5 months):

- Tingling sensations in extremities
- Persistent fatigue and lethargy
- Excessive hair loss
- Pain and stiffness in calf muscles

Medical History:

- Initial Vitamin B12 Level (03March 2024): 12 pg/mL (severe deficiency)
- Treated with injectable Vitamin B12, improving levels to 1233 pg/mL (26 March 2024).
- As soon as the injections were stopped, the Vitamin B12 levels dropped again to 143 pg/mL (01 june 2024)

General examination

The vital signs were all within normal limits: body temperature at 98.0 °F, pulse rate at 82 beats per minute, and blood pressure measuring 120/82 mmHg.

Systemic examination

In the course of the systemic examination, the respiratory and cardiovascular systems displayed no abnormalities. There is no abnormality seen.

Therapeutic Interventions: *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti* is planned for 16 days. (2 sittings with 15 days gap).
 Schedule of *Kala Vasti* -1st A + 6N & 6A (Alternately) + 3 A

A - *Anuvasana*, N - *Niruha*

Interventional Plan – Shown in table No. 1

Table No.1

POORVA KARMA (Preparatory Stage)	PRADHANA KARMA (Main Therapy)	PASHCHATA KARMA (Post-treatment Care)
<p><i>Abhyanga</i> (Oil massage) with <i>Ksheerbala</i> oil. (<i>Sarvanga</i>)</p> <p><i>Swedana</i> (Sudation therapy) with <i>Dashmoola Kashaya</i>. (<i>Sarvanga</i>)</p>	<p><i>Niruha Basti</i> Contents:</p> <p>(a) <i>Makshika</i> (honey) -60ml (b) <i>Saindhava lavana</i> -10gm (c) <i>Sneha</i> (Tila Taila) - 60ml (d) <i>Kalka</i> (<i>Ashwagandha Churna</i> + <i>Shatpushpa Churna</i>) - 50gm (e) <i>Kwath</i> (<i>Vidarikanda</i> + <i>Yashtimadhu</i> + <i>Shringataka</i> + <i>Kasheruka</i>) - 300ml</p> <p><i>Anuvasana Basti</i> with <i>Murchita Tila Taila</i> – 100ml</p>	<p>(a) Dietary Modifications: Vitamin B12-rich foods like milk, curd, cheese, eggs, fish, meat etc.</p> <p>(b) Lifestyle Recommendations: <i>Pranayama</i> and meditation to reduce stress and enhance metabolism.</p>

Route of administration – anal route

No complications have been seen during the *Basti* treatment.

Timeline: Table No.2

Date	Treatment	Dose
18-06-24 to 03-07-24	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>	100ml
1 st Sitting of <i>Vidarikandadi Kala Basti</i>	<i>Niruha Basti</i>	480ml
04-07-24 to 18-07-24 Gap duration between the sittings	Patient was under dietary modifications	
19-07-24 to 03-08-24	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>	100ml
2 nd Sitting of <i>Vidarikandadi Kala Basti</i>	<i>Niruha Basti</i>	480ml

Results - Clinical observations have shown in table No.3

Table No.3

Associated Symptoms	Before-treatment	1 st follow up (after 1 st sitting)	2 nd follow up (after 2 nd sitting)
Tingling sensation	Severe	Mild	Absent
Calf muscle pain	Moderate	Mild	Absent
Hair loss	Severe	Moderate	Mild
Fatigue	8/10	4/10	1/10

Laboratory findings: shown in table No.4

Table No.4

Date	Vitamin B12 Level (pg/mL)	Interpretation
3 rd March 2024	12	Severe deficiency
26 th March 2024 (Post-injectables)	1233	Improved
1 st June 2024	143	Level dropped
18 th August 2024 (Post-ayurvedic treatment)	266	Improved

Following treatment, the patient reported improvement in tingling sensation, calf pain, fatigue and hair loss. Serum Vitamin B12 levels increased from 143 pg/mL to 266 pg/mL during the observation period. While these findings suggest a positive clinical trend, conclusions regarding efficacy cannot be drawn from a single case.

DISCUSSION

Basti (medicated enema) is a core treatment modality in *Panchakarma* for elimination of *Doshas* (*Vata-Pitta-Kapha*) as well as nourishing tissues (*Rasayana Chikitsa*), improving nutrient absorption, and addressing chronic deficiencies. *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti* composed of *Vidarikand*, *Yashtimadhu*, *Shringhatka* and *Kasheruk Dravya*, which have the properties- *Guru*, *Madhura*, *Sheeta Virya*, *Vrushya*, *Balya*, *Rasayna* and *Vata-Pittshamaka*. All these factors collectively do the *Bhrinhana Karma* (*Dhatu Pushti*). The synergistic action of these herbs could potentially facilitate better assimilation of nutrients, including Vitamin B12, even in individuals with dietary restrictions.

Mandagni is the major cause in the pathogenesis of *Pandu Vyadhi*. *Basti* works on *Pachakagni*, as it is stated in classics that after *Basti Karma* there is *Agni Vridhi* (*Deeptagni*) and is also normalizes *Dhatavagni* respectively. Hence, in presence of normal state of *Agni* there is proper formation of *Rasa Dhatu* and so on. From an Ayurvedic perspective, correction of *Agni* and improvement of *Dhatu* nourishment may contribute to symptomatic improvement. However, the relationship between these concepts and biochemical Vitamin B12 status requires further scientific investigation. Contents of *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti* with virtue of their properties may enhance digestive fire (*Agni*), improve absorption, and provide systemic rejuvenation.

Basti may influences gut flora to increase the endogenous synthesis of Vitamin B12. The rectal route permits systemic exposure to administered medicinal substances through a highly vascular mucosal surface. However, the specific effect of *Basti* therapy on Vitamin B12 absorption remains to be elucidated. Vitamin B12 deficiency-related symptoms (numbness, fatigue, tingling) are often interpreted as *Vata* disorder (*Vatavyadhi*). *Basti* is the prime treatment to pacify *Vata* in its root site (colon). So correction of *Vata* balance, in turn leads to subside the symptoms

Pharmacodynamics of drugs^{7,8,9} – shown in table No.5**Table No.5**

S.No	<i>Dravya</i>	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Virya</i>	<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Doshakarma</i>
1	<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vatapittashamaka</i>
2	<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vatapittashamaka</i>
3	<i>Kasheruka</i>	<i>Madhura Kashaya</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Pittashamaka</i>
4	<i>Shringataka</i>	<i>Madhura Kashaya</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Pittashamaka</i>

CONCLUSION

This case report describes symptomatic improvement and an increase in serum Vitamin B12 levels in a patient with recurrent Vitamin B12 deficiency following treatment with *Vidarikandadi Kala Basti*. Although the temporal association is noteworthy, a causal relationship cannot be established because of the single-patient design, absence of a control group and concurrent dietary interventions. The findings may serve as preliminary clinical observations for future research exploring the supportive role of Panchakarma in nutritional deficiencies. Well-designed clinical studies with larger sample sizes are necessary before definitive conclusions can be drawn.

Informed consent

Written consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of this case study.

Limitations:

- Single case study
- No long-term follow-up
- Lack of control group

Future research should include clinical trials with larger cohorts and longer follow-ups to establish statistical and therapeutic validity.

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